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DETECTION OF FAKE ACCOUNTS IN INSTAGRAM USING MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

With the advent of the Internet and social media, while hundreds of people have benefitted from the vast sources of information available, there has been an enormous increase in the rise of cyber-crimes, particularly targeted towards women. According to a 2019 report in the [4] Economics Times, India has witnessed a 457% rise in cybercrime in the five year span between 2011 and 2016. Most speculate that this is due to impact of social media such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter on our daily lives. While these definitely help in creating a sound social network, creation of user accounts in these sites usually needs just an email-id. A real life person can create multiple fake IDs and hence impostors can easily be made. Unlike the real world scenario where multiple rules and regulations are imposed to identify oneself in a unique manner (for example while issuing one's passport or driver's license), in the virtual world of social media, admission does not require any such checks. In this paper, we study the different accounts of Instagram, in particular and try to assess an account as fake or real using Machine Learning techniques namely Logistic Regression and Random Forest Algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Logistic Regression, Random Forest Algorithm, median imputation, Maximum likelihood estimation, k cross validation, overfitting, out of bag data, recall, identity theft, Angler phishing.

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MONITORING STUDENT ATTENDANCE USING A SMART SYSTEM AT TAIF UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The university system in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is concerned with student attendance for lectures, and it is the responsibility of lecturers to monitor student attendance for each lecture. By the end of the semester, students get an attendance register indicating which lectures the student has attended and it reports the calculated percentage for each student's attendance in each course. Universities have regulated the mechanisms and the acceptable percentages of student absence. The process for a lecturer to manually check student attendance consumes a lot of time and effort, either during the lecture or when in the process of emptying absenteeism and inserting it into the university's electronic system. Therefore, Saudi universities compete to find modern methods of checking student attendance that will avoid the disadvantages of manually taking attendance. For this reason, they have produced electronic attendance systems, for example, using a student's fingerprint, an eye recognition system, or a mobile phone system to read a QR code designed for the same purpose. All of these systems have the disadvantage that they consume a lot of time, as all students have to line up at the fingerprint reader or the eye detector for identification. Therefore, the problem of the consumption of lecture time is still present, even with these modern systems. Therefore, the aim of this research is to propose a smart mobile application that is able to check the attendance of students without having to consume lecture time or require any effort from the lecturer. The system automatically recognizes the attendance of students through their university ID cards. Each lecturer would use his/ her own mobile phone to use the proposed system to check the attendance of students instead of using manual method to register the attendance of students and the students' ID cards that are detected by coming within range of the lecturer reader would represent present students, and missing student ID cards represent absent students.

KEYWORDS

Context Awareness, RFID, Monitoring Student Attendance.

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WEB-BASED LEARNING IN PERIODS OF CRISIS: REFLECTIONS ON THE IMPACT OF COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

Education systems and its actors are generally responding to quarantine and large-scale shutdown (partial) of cities with a sudden shift to Web-Based Learning. However, given that a pandemic of this nature and scale is novel, there is a knowledge gap as to how teachers and learners should respond to the shift, and what the likely impact and the key considerations should be. This study aims to extrapolate and theorize from the existing knowledgebase about the use of Web-Based Learning, as well as from an expert and practitioner wisdom and experience, to offer high-level guidance for policymakers and education system actors that are forced to make decisions in fast-moving and very challenging circumstances with little guidance or relevant experience. It is an early attempt at theorizing the impact of the pandemic on two key actors (Learners and Teachers) and one interface (Content), all across eight dimensions of learning. The analysis is based on Khan's (2001) dimension of Web-Based Learning and Anderson's (2011) Model of Online Learning. Overall, we posit based on experience and practice, that the pandemic has delivered severe shocks to both the demand and supply side of Web-Based Learning, with Learners, Teachers, and Content all significantly affected. While we hypothesize a general drop in the quality of teaching and learning in the short run, we expect the opposite to be the case in the long run, when the demand and supply side self-correct, albeit guided by strong government and market institutions.

KEYWORDS

Web-Based Learning, COVID-19, Learners

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SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

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BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

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